

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 1, No. 11; November 28, 1995

Dear Readers:

here is the last-but-one number of J.UCS of 1995: and with it a pleasant surprise. Springer Publ. Co. will press 30.000 CD ROM's that will contain the first volume (1995) of J.UCS (all papers!) together with information on all material available from Springer. This CD ROM will be distributed free of charge, and will thus bring J.UCS to thousands of users.

Thus, all papers that have appeared in J.UCS in 1995 will receive much more publicity than any author could ever have expected! Because of this we encourage everyone to still consider submitting a paper for the December issue: we will try to review some of them within 2 weeks so they still can go into the first volume of J.UCS and hence onto the CD ROM mentioned. This will only be possible for those papers where we manage to find superfast referees, where no changes are necessary and the format is exactly as required for J.UCS.

The printed version of volume 1 will appear in March 96.

Hope you enjoy this issue of J.UCS...which is more applied than most previous ones!

Cheers,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Dr. H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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